

Changing Rural Population Trends: A Case Study of Shrigonda, Ahmednagar (Maharashtra)

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ABSTRACT:

Shrigonda tahsil is located in the southern drought-prone zone of Ahmednagar district. The tahsil situated partly in upper Saraswati basin and partly Bhima, Ghod and Kukadi basin. It is surrounded by Parner and Nagar tahsil to the northern part, Pune district to the west and south east Karjat tahsil. It's an area of 1630 sq.km; the third rank of tahsil in Ahmednagar district. Tahsil has historical and religious background and situated on the bank of river Saraswati. The latitudinal extent is 18° 27'18" to 18° 51'54" North and longitudinal extent is 74° 23'24" to 74° 52' East. The Shrigonda tahsil is mainly rural in character and has 114 villages according to 2011 census.

The study is useful in understanding the importance of Population for rural development. This understanding certainly helps in the planning for integrated information of rural areas and in deciding policies. The study based on primary and secondary data. Primary data collected with help of Questionnaire form various household and secondary data collected from census and Government documents. It is based on 10 percent samples household form Selected villages.

The human resource is one of the vital resources of a region. The information on this aspect considered population characteristics like population growth, density, literacy, sex ratio, In the study of socio – economic importance of population analysis has been considered essential by most of the scholars because all these aspects are closely related. The study is mainly concerned with population characteristics and geographic factors. Population distribution, density and size of villages are dependent upon the geographical condition of that particular area. Relief, climate, soil, water resource, socio-economic and cultural factors are responsible for the distribution and density of population.

Growing population is considered and analyse the situation of rural areas in Ahmednagar district households.

Keywords: Population composition, Socio-economic, Development, Human Resource, Analysis, Trend, Population Characteristics, Rural Area.

INTRODUCTION:

The ultimate goal of any planned development of the society is the multifaced improvement of living conditions of the people. Man is not only the creator of all forms of national wealth, but also ultimate goal of whole gamut of economic and social activities. Today man occupies a central position around which

all activities – economic, social and political revolve.

An integrated programme for the utilization of Population should include long terms aims and instruments for the development of human capacities for economic and social development. The development of population through education and vocational training should, therefore, be accorded a very high

priority in the future planning and programme of economic development.

Growing population has both quantitative and qualitative dimensions. Characteristics like the size, composition and distribution of population and skilled labor force, literacy level, the number of hours worked, the output and earnings per head etc. are qualitatively measurable and therefore lend themselves to statistical treatment. The qualitative characteristics like knowledge, skills, aptitudes values and motivations etc. often lack conceptual and national clarity and precision and do not lend themselves to statistical treatment as the quantitative characteristics.

In the study of socio - economic importance of population analysis has been considered essential by most of the scholars because all these aspects are closely related. The study is mainly concerned with population characteristics and geographic factors. Population distribution, density and size of villages are dependent upon the geographical condition of that particular area. Relief, climate, soil, water resource, socio-economic and cultural factors are responsible for the distribution and density of population.

We are studying the micro-level, which means the study area is divided for six village groups and they have included in sub-villages. The socio-economic study included this topic is main important parameter of development in various villages as compare to another Tahsil, as well as district. Therefore the important part of micro-level study in rural area for development of any region.

The development of the region is concerned with the quality and quantity of the population. Saptarshi (1996) has described that the potential of human population as a resource is determined by its social, cultural and economic characteristics as well as by the level of technological development. According to Dutta and Sundaram (1996) the quality of population can be judged from life expectancy, the level of literacy and the level of technical training attained by the people of a country.

OBJECTIVE:

1. The present study to analyze the changing trends of population in rural areas of Shrigonda tahsil.

STUDY AREA:

The Shrigonda tahsil is located in the southern drought prone zone of Ahmednagar district. The tahsil situated partly Bhima, Ghod and Kuakdi River and canal basin. In the tahsil length of 60 Km. from East to West and 51 Km. from North to South. The height of tahsil is recorded 600 mtr. Above the sea level. Generally slope of tahsil is North to South.

The latitudinal extend is $18^{\circ} 27' 18''$ to $18^{\circ} 51' 54''$ North and longitudinal extend is $74^{\circ} 23' 24''$ to $74^{\circ} 52'$ East. It is surrounded by Parner and Nagar tahsil to the northern part, Pune district to the west and south - east Karjat tahsil. It's an area of 1630 Sq. Km. is the third rank of tahsil in Ahmednagar district. It is historical and religious which is situated on the bank of river Saraswati.

Location Map of Shrigonda Tahsil

Fig.No.01

METHODOLOGY:

The parametric approach has been adopted to quantify manpower in the study area. They are devoted to discuss those parameters of population, which are associated with the human resources. The village wise information regarding such parameters has been procured and analyzed to understand the causes and effects of Population development. We use the Quantitative methods which are to related population density, growth, literacy, sex ratio with the help of charts and graphs.

The present paper is primarily based on secondary data. The data on decadal year for the census year have been collected. Considering a village as a unit for the shrigonda tahsil in Ahmednagar district of Maharashtra, the data have been collected of village

Panchyat Samiti, Tahsil office Shrigonda, Socio-economic review book, statistical abstract of Ahmednagar district. The data pertaining to the period from 1971 to 2011 (Population Structure) as per 10 year gap between two decades. Since the study area is large enough for detailed socio-economic survey and analysis it has not been possible to study on village level data. Primarily the study is based on block level published and unpublished data we are studying the methods necessity to subject. e.g. population density, growth, sex ratio, literacy, etc.

POPULATION SIZE OF VILLAGES:

According to 2001 census the population group has been divided in to seven groups. They have showing on 500 to 50000 included for village population.

Table No. 1: Population Distribution of Villages, 2011

Population	Groups Of Villages						No. of Villages
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	
> 500	0	1 (16.06)	0	1 (16.06)	2 (33.3)	2 (33.3)	6 (05.26)
500 - 999	1 (6.66)	4 (26.66)	1 (01.66)	5 (33.33)	1 (06.66)	3 (20)	15 (13.15)
1000 - 1499	4 (18.18)	0	7 (31.81)	2 (09.09)	3 (13.63)	6 (27.27)	22 (19.29)
1500 - 4999	6 (09.83)	7 (11.47)	17 (27.86)	8 (13.11)	13 (21.31)	10 (16.39)	61 (53.50)
5000 - 9999	1 (12.50)	2 (25)	0	3 (37.50)	1 (12.50)	1 (12.50)	8 (07.01)
10000- 49999	1 (50)	1 (50)	0	0	0	0	2
< 50000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total no. of Villages	13 (11.40)	15 (13.15)	25 (21.92)	19 (16.66)	20 (17.54)	22 (19.29)	114

(Source: - District Census Handbook, Ahmednagar District)

I - Limpangaon , II - Belwandi Bk. , III - Yelpane,
IV - Kolgaon , V - mandavgan , VI - Adhalgaon

Table below provides villages by population size and their percent to total inhabited villages in the Tahsil. Shrigonda Tahsil out of 114 inhabited villages, in the Tahsil 06 (5.26 per cent) have a population of below 500, 15(13.15 per cent) are in the size class 500 - 999, 22 (19.29 per cent) In the size class, 1000 - 1499, 61 (53.50 per cent) in the size class 1500 - 4999, 08 (7.01 per cent) in the category 5000 - 9999, 02 (1.75 per cent) in the population range of 10000 - 49999

and exceptionally large sized (50000+) is not anyone inhabited villages. With the Tahsil, small sized villages of less than 500 account for 5.26 per cent, of medium sized (1500 - 4999) 53.50 per cent of the total inhabited villages, (5000 - 9999) large sized of population villages is 7.01 per cent and very large sized (10000 - 49999) group of population in 1.75 per cent villages. There are no anyone village in last group (more than 50000).

Population According to Size of Villages:

Table No. 2

Sr.No.	Village Size	No. Of Villages	Per Cent Of Villages	Population	Per Cent Of Population In Each Size
1	> 500	06	05	2160	0.75
2	500 - 999	15	13	11672	4.09
3	1000 - 1499	22	19	25981	9.12
4	1500 - 4999	61	54	162122	56.91
5	5000 - 9999	08	07	56504	19.83
6	10000 - 49999	02	02	26402	9.26
7	< 50000	0	0	0	0
	Total	114	100	284841	100

(Source: - District census handbook, 2011)

According to 2011 census showing on table in Tahsil population according to size of villages. The village population size in below 500 to above 50000 difference classes showing on size and population. The total villages of Tahsil are 114, in this village's distribution of population in various size groups. Below 500 size group is smallest group showing number villages is six (06) and per cent of villages in 05 included to population is 1828 (0.70 per cent) in this group lowest population size group.

The highest village size groups in 1500 - 4999 this groups included on 61 villages (54 per cent) and 162122 population (56.91 per cent), second highest group is 5000 - 9999 included 08

villages (7 per cent) and including for 56504 population (19.83 per cent), next is 1000 - 1499 group included on 22 villages (19 per cent) including 25981 population (9.12 per cent). In largest group of village size is 10000 to 49999 including only two villages (2 per cent) and they have showing on 26402 (9.26 per cent) population and second group of size 500 to 999 including on 15 villages (13 per cent) they have showing on 11672 population (4.09 per cent). In this table showing on scenario of total Tahsil and including village population size. These table helping for development in socio-economic condition in shrigonda Tahsil.

POPULATION GROWTH RATE:

Table No.03: Population Growth Rate In Shrigonda Tahsil 1951 - 2011 (In Per Cent)

Village Name	61 - 71	81 - 91	01-11	Chang in per cent 61-11
Limpangaon	52.00	35.24	18.72	-64.00
Belwandi Bk.	32.91	44.97	06.20	-81.16
Yelpane	12.48	32.88	12.23	-2.00
Kolgaon	17.61	23.86	15.13	-14.13
Mandavgan	18.60	20.55	14.88	-20.00
Adhalgaon	24.99	32.98	07.77	-68.90
Total Villages	24.08	31.24	09.72	-59.63
Total Town	22.17	35.73	18.27	-17.59
Total Tahsil	23.90	31.64	12.87	-46.15

(Source: -District census handbook, Ahmednagar)

Fig. No. 02

The table No. 03 shows the population and growth rate in percent of main six groups in Shrigonda tahsil namely Limpangaon, Belwandi Bk., Yelpane, Kolgaon, Mandavgan and Adhalgaon. Whole groups are commonly distributed population. Minimum population located in Limpangaon group (9292) and maximum population recorded in Yelpane group (18477) according to 1951 census. According to 2011 census maximum population recorded a Yelpane group (52973) and minimum population recorded at Mandavgan group (43679).

According to 1961-71 census Yelpane group shows minimum growth rate of population which was 12.48 percent and also fifty percent lower than the total Shrigonda tahsil (23.90 percent) as a whole. In this year Limpangaon group showing maximum growth rate of population which was in 52 percent and this compare to double in total tahsil (23.90 percent) population growth rate. The another group is Belwandi Bk. (32.19 percent), Kolgaon (17.61 percent), Mandavga (18.60 percent), and Adhalgaon (24.99 percent) growth of population which was higher in Belwadi Bk. and Adhalogan group and lower in Kolgaon and Mandavgan group in total tahsil growth rate. The total villages growth rate was slightly increasing (24.08 percent) than the total tahsil (23.90 percent) and total town or city (22.17 percent) growth rate according to 1961-71 census.

According to 1981-91 census Mandavgan group shows minimum growth rate of population, which was 20.55 percent lower than the total growth rate of Shrigonda tahsil (31.64 percent) as

a whole. In this year Belwandi Bk. group showing maximum growth rate of population which was in 44.97 percent and this compare to more than total tahsil (31.64 percent) population growth rate. Another group is Limpangaon (35.24 percent), Yelpane (32.88 percent), Kolgaon (23.86 percent), and Adhalgaon (32.98 percent) growth of population, which was higher in Limpangaon and Adhalgaon group and lower in Kolgaon group in total tahsil growth rate. The total villages growth rate was slightly decreasing (31.24 percent) than the total tahsil (31.64 percent) and total town or city (35.73 percent) growth rate was increasing to total villages and tahsil according to 1981-91 census.

According to 2001-11 census Belwandi Bk. group shows minimum growth rate of population which was 6.20 percent lower than the total tahsil (12.87 percent). In this year Limpangaon group showing maximum growth rate of population (18.72 percent). Another group is Kolgaon 15.13 percent, Mandavgan 14.88 percent, Yelpane 12.23 percent and Adhalgaon 7.77 percent growth of population. The total villages growth rate decreasing 9.72 percent than the total tahsil 12.87 percent and total town 18.27 percent.

According to table No. 03 shows change of growth rate in 1961 to 2011 was variations of groups. Limpangaon group shows maximum change (Negative) of population growth was -64.00 percent and Yelpane group showing on minimum change (Negative) (-2.00 percent) growth rate of population. Average of total villages (-59.63 percent) and total tahsil (17.59 percent) is similar than the total

town growth rate of population (-46.15 percent).

Where nearest group located from Shrigonda tahsil resulted the more people concentrated for education, administration and other social and economic services. The table No. 03 showing that growth rate is decreased (Negative) in a tahsil is ascertained by only three factors; fertility, mortality and migration for the growth of population in

POPULATION DENSITY:

Table No. 04: Population Density

Village Name	1971	1991	2011	Per Cent In Change 1971-2011
Limpangaon	330	268	344	04.24
Belwandi Bk.	292	181	245	-16.09
Yelpane	198	123	215	08.58
Kolgaon	220	131	175	-20.45
Mandavgan	205	106	132	-35.60
Adhalgaon	191	122	166	-13.08
Total Villages	86	138	193	124.41
Total Town	156	259	372	138.46
Total Tahsil	90	144	208	131.11

(Source: - District census handbook – Ahmednagar.)

Distribution and density are most important and fundamental factors in the study of population geography. Distribution means the spread of population into aerial unit of irregular administrative size. "Density means ratio between the size of population and the area in sq. km." It means man land ratio. Henry D. Harness first used the term, 'Density of population', in 1837 while preparing railway maps for Ireland. This is a ratio between population and area.

The distribution of population on the earth surface is uneven. The studies related to distribution tell us how many people live in which area, which have

tahsil, migration has never been as important factor. The contribution of the other two factors, fertility and mortality, has to be considered. Improved transportation and communication. The growth of the population is increasing therefore decline in death rate, because improvement of medical and other facilities. Control epidemic diseases that's why declining death rate.

concentration of population an which area have very few people. Density of population plays an important part in any scheme related to health, trade and socio-economic development. In short in indicates possibilities of development. Political economic, social aspects of life are influenced by distribution of population.

We calculate the population density of various groups of Shrigonda Tahsil. It is also interesting result and variation from one group to another group. The average density of Shrigonda tahsil was 90 persons per sq. km. According to 1971 census and according

to 2011 census the density of total tahsil was 208 persons per sq. km.

According to 1971 census Adhalgaon group records lowest density of population; which was 191 persons per sq. km. Where Limpangaon group records Maximum population density which was 330 persons per sq. km. In this year total town or city (156 persons per sq. km.) density was greater than the total villages and total tahsil population density (86 and 90 persons per sq. km. respectively). All group's population density was increased than the total villages town and tahsil, which was Belwandi Bk. (292 person per sq. km.), Yelpane (198 person per sq. km.), Kolgaon and Mandavgan (220 and 205 persons per sq. km. respectively).

According to 1991 census Mandavgan group records lowest density of population; which was 106 persons per sq. km. Where Limpangaon group records Maximum population density which was 268 persons per sq. km. In this year total town or city (259 persons per sq. km.) density was greater than the total villages and total tahsil population density (138 and 144 persons per sq. km. respectively). Population density was increased than the total villages town and tahsil, which

was Belwandi Bk. (181 person per sq. km.), Yelpane (123 person per sq. km.), Kolgaon and Adhalgaon (131 and 122 persons per sq. km. respectively).

According to 2011 census Mandavgan groups records lowest density of population which was 132 persons per sq. km. where Limpangaon grop records maximum population density which was 344 person per sq. km. In this year total town (372 person per sq. km.) density was greater than the total villages (193) and total tahsil (208). All over the groups population density was increased that the total villages town and tahsil which was Belwandi Bk. (245) and Yelpane (215).

The table No. 04 shows the change of population density in percent compare to 1971 to 2011 census. Kolgaon group records lower (-13.08 percent) growth of population where as Yelpane group records maximum (8.58 percent) growth of population density. Village groups recorded 124.41 percent density, total tahsil has been 131.11 percent and total town was 138.46 percent population density. In this characteristics affecting for the physical or natural, cultural and social factors to increasing or decreasing the density of population.

Fig. No.03

Rural village density as compare to town density is lower than the 1971 to 2011 and change is same the village density (124.41 per cent). Town density is increasing because various amenities are available to town e.g. education, medical,

employment, social and cultural etc. so the people are attract to the city area. Density has been increasing or decreasing depends on impact in physical and social factor.

LITERACY:

Table No. 05: Literacy in Shrigonda Tahsil (in per cent)

Sr. No.	Village Name	1971	1991	2011	Change Per Cent In 1971-2011
1	Limpangaon	32.04	43.94	65.72	105.21
2	Belwandi Bk.	34.73	47.04	68.03	95.88
3	Yelpane	35.57	44.58	65.32	83.63
4	Kolgaon	35.67	49.77	67.46	89.12
5	Mandavgan	28.48	43.35	65.05	128.40
6	Adhalgaon	27.24	46.51	66.48	144.05
	<i>Total Villages</i>	33.17	45.59	66.35	100.03
	Total Town	37.20	58.72	72.31	94.38
	Total Tahsil	33.33	46.31	66.94	100.84

(Source: - District Census Handbook, Ahmednagar)

One of the important indicators of social development is the level of literacy and educational attainment. A high level of which is considered to be an important factor in the process of modernization. Education is an important variable affecting demographic behavior concerning marriage, fertility, mortality, migration as well as participation in the labor force. One who can read and write his name is considered a literate person (United Nations Organization). One who can read but cannot write is considered 'semi-literate'. According to census of India, "a person who can both read and write with understanding in any language is to be taken as literate."

Table No. 5 and figure No. 4 shows literacy of Shrigonda tahsil and groups. Above data day by day literacy is increase. According to 1971 census the highest

literacy found in Kolgaon group i.e. 35.67 percent and lowest literacy in Adhalgaon group that was 27.24 percent. Another group's literacy was moderate like Limpangaon (32.04 percent), Belwandi Bk. (34.73 percent), Yelpane (35.57 percent), and Mandavgan (28.48 percent). The total town or city literacy rate was increasing in 1971 i.e. 37.20 percent than the total villages and total tahsil (33.17 and 33.33 percent respectively).

According to 1991 census the highest literacy found in again Kolgaon group i.e. 49.77 percent and lowest literacy in Mandavgan group that was 43.35 percent. Another group's literacy is moderate like Limpangaon (43.94 percent), Belwandi Bk. (47.04 percent), Yelpane (44.58 percent) and Adhalgaon (46.51 percent). The total town or city literacy rate was increasing according to

1991 census i.e. 58.72 percent than the total villages and total tahsil (45.59 and 46.31 percent respectively).

The table no. 05 shows in 2011 census the highest literacy found Belwandi Bk. group i.e. 68.03 percent and lowest Mandavgan group that was 65.05 percent. Other four groups literacy ratio is moderate like Limpangaon 65.72 percent, Yelpane 65.32 percent, Kolgaon 67.46 percent, Adhalgaon 66.48 percent. The total town or city literacy rate was increasing according to 2011 census i.e. 72.31 percent than the total villages and total tahsil 66.35 percent and 66.94 percent respectively.

The all over the group literacy rate was positive from day by day because human development growth was positive from society.

The table No. 5 shows the change of Literacy in percent compare to 1971 to 2011 census. Yelpane group records lower (83.63 percent) growth of literacy. Whereas Adhalgaon group records maximum (144.05 percent) growth of Literacy. Village groups recorded 100.03 percent Literacy, total tahsil has been 100.84 percent and total town was 94.38 percent Literacy.

According to table and figure the growth rate of literacy was increasing or

positive in day by day. Because people awareness and importance of education in human life is essential. This characteristic of basic need for human development.

Proportion of literates is low for rural areas. There is low of educational facilities in rural areas. Similarly, there is absence of proper environment and social organization most important role for to contribute increase the literacy rate. E.g. Government started "Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan", "Chock and blackboard operation", have achieve goal to know anyone illiterate in 2010. Another important matter the female literacy is very less than the male during the 2011 male literacy is 73.32 per cent and female is 60.01 per cent. Normally, proportion of literates is higher among males than that among females. This is so particularly in the developing region. This is because of lower social status of women in that region. In rural areas parents are not very keen to educate their daughters. In addition to this, lower age at marriage for girls and household work they are required to do, also contribute towards lower proportion of literates among females.

Fig. No. 4

Today, people have known to importance of education therefore the growth of literacy higher. The progress of male and female literacy in tahsil from 1901 to 2011 is presented in table and figure. The results of the 2011 census also indicated that there has been a decline in the absolute number of illiterates, for the first time since independent during 1901 – 2011. This has been considered as a

major shift to improving the literacy in India and as well as our study area.

SEX RATIO:

The sex ratio is very important characteristics in population studies. The following table No. 06 and figure No. 05 explain the sex ratio of various Zillah parishad groups in Shrigonda tahsil.

Table No. 6: Sex Ratio In Shrigonda Tahsil (Per Thousand Male)

Sr.No.	Village Name	1971	1991	2011	Change Per Cent In 1971-2001
1	Limpangaon	961	915	922	-4.05
2	Belwandi Bk.	948	951	909	-4.11
3	Yelpane	895	966	926	3.46
4	Kolgaon	973	973	918	-5.65
5	Mandavgan	966	953	931	-3.62
6	Adhalgaon	972	923	919	-5.45
	Total Villages	951	947	920	-3.36
	Total Town	941	935	940	-0.10
	Total Tahsil	950	946	923	-2.92

(Source: - District Census Handbook, Ahmednagar).

Sex ratio of population is also an important aspect of as well as vital role in socio-economic development. Sex composition of married persons in a population and birth rate. If proportion of males in the total population is larger than that for females. If proportion of males in a population is large, age at marriage for girls declines.

Showing on the table No.6 shows sex ratio various groups according to 1971 to 2011 census. According to 1971 census same condition for sex ratio in 1951 and 1961 census. Kolgaon group recorded 973 females per thousand males and which was highest in all groups in Shrigonda tahsil. Total villages recorded 951 sex ratio, which was slightly increasing to, all Shrigonda tahsil sex ratio

(950). Total town or city sex ratio was lowest (944 females per thousand males) to total villages and tahsil. As compare to total tahsil (945) sex ratio. Other groups i.e. Limpangaon (961), Mandavgan (966) and Adhalgaon (972) females per thousand males was highest ratio than the total tahsil. Belwandi Bk. group sex ratio (948) was lowest than the total tahsil sex ratio. Any groups recorded highest sex ratio due to male migration towards nearest nearest urban centers. Only Belwandi group sex ratio was lowest as compare to total tahsil sex ratio. People migrate to daily occupation for earnings. According to 1961 census same situation for previous decade in sex ratio.

In 1991 census Kolgaon group recorded 973 females per thousand males

and which was maximum in all in Shrigonda tahsil. The Limpangaon group (915) sex ratio was minimum in this decade. Total villages recorded 947 sex ratio, which was slightly increasing than the all Shrigonda tahsil sex ratio (946). Total town or city sex ratio was lowest (935 females per thousand males) to total villages and tahsil. As compare to total tahsil (935) sex ratio. Other Zillah parishad groups i.e. Belwandi Bk. (951), Yelpane (966), Mandavgan (953), females per thousand males was maximum ratio than the total tahsil (946) sex ratio and Adhalgaon group recorded minimum sex ratio (923) to tahsil. According to 1991 census.

In 2011 census Mandavgan group recorded 931 females per thousand males and which was maximum in village group in tahsil. The Belwandi Bk. group 909 sex ratio was minimum in this decade. Total villages recorded 920 sex ratio, which was lowest than the town and tahsil (940 and 923 respectively) other village groups i.e. Limpangaon (922), Yelpane (926), Kolgaon (918) and Adhalgaon (919), females per thousand males according to 2011 census.

Table No.06 shows the change in percent compare with 1971 to 2011 data. All over the sex ratio was negative Kolgaon group sex ratio (-5.65). Shrigonda tahsil as a whole recorded -

2.92 percent sex ratio as compare to six decades. Minimum change recorded at Kolgaon group (-5.65 percent) and maximum sex ratio change recorded in Yelpane group (3.46 percent). All the Village groups recording decreasing in trends of sex ratio.

Female percent was decreasing in day-by-day. Mortality among females is higher in the age group of 5 to 15 years in the developing region due to inadequacy of medical facilities and under nutrition. Proportion of females in total population further declines because of high maternal mortality. If we compare sex ratio for Shrigonda Tahsil in 2011 with that in 1971, it shows that benefits of development have been cornered by males, which resulted in an increase in proportion of males in total population. Village's total sex ratio in 1971 was 951 and it was 920 for 2011. Change between 50 years -3.36 percent.

Males number than the females in total population of the region due to inferior status of females, mortality among females is high and that is why males number females in the total population. Males have dominated sex ratio for population of tahsil since long. Among those dying to epidemic diseases and due to inadequate medical facilities, proportion of female is quite high.

Fig. No.5

Sex ratio is effect on religious group, tribal population, physiography of region etc. Yelpane group is positive change. Because in this group near from Pune district, Ranjangaon, Chakan, Shikrapur located big MIDC therefore people migrate to various purposes. So the impact for sex male population is low than the female. Belwandi (-4.51 per cent) and Mandavgan (-5.00) groups have high negative change because in this region tribal population settle and low literacy rate therefore effect from sex ratio. Another group from Limpagaon, Kolgaon and Adhalgaon (-6.01, -7.32, -5.06 respectively) groups most of effect from sex ratio is topography and scarcity of water, malnutrition etc. therefore negative impact for mortality in female population. Inferior status of women is the society and predominance of males among migrants.

All this discussion clearly shows that the results of the 2011 census further indicated that although the overall sex ratio has declined. Thus it was pointed out that the proportion of boys among the new born babies is increasing sharply and it is commonly assumed to be the result of the rapid spread of the use of ultrasound and amniocentesis for sex determination and subsequent sex selective induced abortion. Amarty sen refers to the abortions of the female fetus after determination of the sex of the fetus as "natality inequality". He designates the use of ultrasound as "high-tech sexism". The National Family Health Survey (NFHS-2) 1998-99 provided convincing evidence that sex-selective abortion is a common practice in many parts of India. The information available from the NFHS-2 and sex ratios at birth, abortions, the

use of ultrasound and amniocentesis, and the degree of son preferences in India, presents a consistent picture of the widespread use of sex-selective abortions.

CONCLUSION:

Shrigonda tahsil located Southern part of Ahmednagar district. In this tahsil we observed great variety of population composition. Shrigonda tahsil come under rain shadow zone characterized by hot summer and general dryness. Rainfall records 522 mm. annually. Temperature increases more than 44^oC in summer and comes up to 11.7^oC in December. Shrigonda tahsil shows physical variation with platues and Bhima-Ghod plain. Bhima and Ghod are important rivers in tahsil. Soil is characterized with kali, red, tambat and barad; Bhima and Ghod basin lies in tashil, which is potential for agricultural development.

The study trace on Population structure situation in tahsil. Population growth, composition of population, Sex ratio, Literacy is studied.

In Human Geography population and neural phenomena are studied and analyze the prospects and difficulties in regions. Population of Shrigonda tahsil recorded about 61240 according to 1901 census. After 110 years population of tahsil increase more than five times and reach up to 315975 according to 2011 census. The village population size in below 500 to above 50000 difference classes showing on size and population. The highest village size groups in 1500 – 4999 this groups included on 61 villages (54 per cent) and 162122 population (56.91 per cent). The growth rate in 1971 to 2001 was variations of groups. Adhalgaon group shows maximum change

(Negative) of population growth was - 68.90 percent and Yelpane group showing on minimum change (Negative) (-2.00 percent) growth rate of population. Average of total villages (-59.63 percent) and total tahsil (-46.15 percent) is similar than the total town growth rate of population (-17.59 percent). The growth rate is increased in a tahsil is ascertained by only three factors; fertility, mortality and migration for the growth of population in tahsil, migration has never been as important factor. Rural village density as compare to town density is lower than the 1971 to 2011 but change is higher than the village density (124.41 per cent). Town density is increasing because various amenities are available to town e.g. education, medical, employment, social and cultural etc.

According to table and figure the growth rate of literacy was increasing or positive in day by day. Because people awareness and importance of education in human life is essential. This characteristic of basic need for human development. Proportion of literates is low for rural areas. There is low of educational facilities in rural areas. Literacy in percent compare to 1971 to 2011 census. Mandavgan group records lower (-35.60 percent) growth of literacy. Whereas Yelpane group records maximum (8.58 percent) growth of Literacy. All groups recorded 124.41 percent Literacy, total tahsil has been 131.11 percent and total town was 138.46 percent Literacy. Another aspect of population composition is sex ratio. Sex ratio expresses the number of female per thousand of male population. According to 1901 census sex ratio of shrigonda tahsil was 962 females per thousand males. In 1971 this ratio decrease up to

950 females per 1000 males and recently (2011) sex ratio of Shrigonda tahsil recorded 923 females per 1000 male population. For social stability and balance of family structure it is necessary to balance of male and female proportion of population. The condition of India as a whole, state and also tahsil female population is less than male population and it is not suitable for cultural stability of society.

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